

Vector Representation of Biological Data Using Machine Learning

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The increasing volume of biological data, such as protein-protein interactions (PPI), presents challenges for analysis and interpretation. This work focuses on representing PPI data, traditionally structured in graph format, in vector form. This approach uses advanced dimensionality reduction techniques to visualize high-dimensional data in manageable forms. By converting PPI data into vector form, we enable more effective clustering and identification of functional relationships between proteins, facilitating the discovery of hidden patterns and insights. This work represents a significant advancement in bioinformatics, offering powerful tools for analyzing complex biological systems and facilitating future research and discoveries.

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I. Introduction

The intersection of biology and computer science created the field of bioinformatics, which uses computational tools to analyze and interpret biological data. One of the challenges in bioinformatics is the representation of complex biological data [1], such as protein-protein interaction (PPI) networks, in a way that enables efficient analysis and knowledge discovery. Traditionally, PPIs have been represented as graphs, but this approach faces limitations when dealing with large-scale datasets. To address this, the concept of vector representation has emerged as a promising solution. By converting complex graph structures into numerical vectors, researchers can apply machine learning techniques to uncover hidden patterns, relationships, and insights within biological data.

I.I. Artificial Intelligence - Machine Learning

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force in various fields, and its impact on biology and medicine is particularly noteworthy. The ability of AI to analyze vast amounts of data, identify patterns, and make predictions has opened new ways for understanding complex biological systems and improving healthcare. Machine learning (ML), a subset of AI, has become a cornerstone in the analysis of biological big data, encompassing diverse data types such as genomic sequences, medical images, and tabular data.

I.II. Biological Data

The discovery of DNA's structure revolutionized biology, leading to an explosion of knowledge and the development of modern biology, with its diverse branches like genetics, biochemistry, and bioinformatics. This revolution, coupled with high-throughput technologies, like NGS, has resulted in a massive influx of biological data, termed "omics" data [2].

The sources of "omics" data are diverse and include genomics and epigenomics, transcriptomics, metabolomics, proteomics, and biomedical data. Genomics and epigenomics provide insights into the genetic makeup of organisms and the modifications that influence gene expression. Transcriptomics reveal the activity of genes and their corresponding RNA transcripts, while metabolomics captures the small molecules involved in cellular processes. Proteomics focuses on the proteins present in a cell or organism, and biomedical data includes clinical information and medical imaging data.

I.III. Scope

In this study, we explore the application of Graph2Vec and Node2Vec techniques to represent PPI networks in vectorized form. We use graph-structured data representing such networks, in various types of cancer. By incorporating advanced techniques and utilizing specialized models, we aim to improve the quality of embeddings and gain deeper insights into the complex relationships within biological networks. The goal is to develop a robust and reliable methodology for representing and analyzing biological data, paving the way for new discoveries and advancements in the field.

II. Material and methods

In this study, we collected PPI network data from the STRING database for 11 common cancer types, focusing on experimentally observed interactions to ensure data reliability and biological relevance.

To analyze the PPI networks, we used two graph representation learning techniques: Graph2Vec and Node2Vec. Graph2Vec was used to generate embeddings for entire PPI networks, while Node2Vec was applied to

learn embeddings for individual proteins within each network.

The Graph2Vec [3] technique was employed to generate vector representations (embeddings) for each PPI network as a whole. This method learns to represent entire graphs as unique vectors in a high-dimensional space, capturing their structural and functional properties. A neural network was trained on the PPI graph data to learn graph embeddings that preserve information about protein structures and interactions.

To obtain vector representations for individual proteins within each PPI network, the Node2Vec [4] technique was utilized. Node2Vec is a graph embedding method that learns continuous feature representations for nodes in networks. It achieves this by simulating random walks through the graph, capturing the local neighborhood structure of each node.

To visualize and analyze the high-dimensional protein embeddings, the t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) was applied for non-linear dimensionality reduction. The target dimensionality was set to 2, allowing for visualization in a 2-dimensional plane. K-means clustering was performed on the reduced embeddings to group proteins based on their functional similarity, aiding in the interpretation and analysis of the results.

III. Results and discussion

The analysis of PPI networks from the STRING database using Graph2Vec and Node2Vec techniques yielded significant insights into the structural and functional relationships within the networks of various cancer types. The results of this study are summarized in three key figures, highlighting the effectiveness of these methods in representing PPI networks.

Figure 1. t-SNE plots of Graph2Vec, with and without the largest two datasets

The t-SNE plots of Graph2Vec embeddings, both with and without the two largest datasets, reveal distinct clustering patterns that indicate the preservation of structural properties in the vector representations. When the largest two datasets are excluded, the embeddings of the remaining datasets don't change significantly. This suggests that the size of the datasets does not significantly contribute to its embedding representation.

In Figure 2, the t-SNE plots of Node2Vec embeddings for the largest two datasets, highlights the effectiveness of Node2Vec in capturing local neighborhood structures within PPI networks, regardless of their size. Each cluster represents proteins with similar interaction patterns.

Figure 2. t-SNE plots of Node2Vec of the largest two datasets (leukemia and cancer), colored by cluster.

The plots of Figure 3 represent good classification examples where the embeddings successfully separate distinct functional clusters. However, not all classifications have been successful or meaningful.

Figure 3. t-SNE plots of Node2Vec of glaucoma and breast cancer, colored by cluster, representing good classification examples.

IV. Conclusions

This study successfully demonstrates that Graph2Vec and Node2Vec techniques effectively capture the structural and functional properties of PPI networks, facilitating their analysis and interpretation. The results highlight the potential of these methods in clustering and classifying complex biological data, aiding in the discovery of disease-specific biomarkers and therapeutic targets. Future research should refine these techniques, integrate different data types, and explore applications in other biological networks to further enhance bioinformatics research.

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